

SOCIAL SCIENCES

SWOT ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF RECREATIONAL SERVICES FOR PREGNANT WOMEN IN BULGARIA

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Abstract

In modern European living conditions, there is a strong need for healthy programs for women with normal pregnancies. There is a need for more and more specialised centers and the provision of new, accessible and different types of motor services to meet the needs of pregnant women who want to play Recreational activities. This development is a market study of wellness services for pregnant women. The aim of this study is to identify some marketing aspects related to the provision of leisure services for pregnant women with normal pregnancies and postpartum women as a prerequisite for improving their quality, strengths and weaknesses, as well as threats and opportunities for the development of recreational motor services for pregnant women in Bulgaria. Literature related to the effects of Recreational activities on the body of a pregnant woman has been studied. A questionnaire method was used with women with normal pregnancies participating in recreational physical activities. A situational analysis of the development of Recreational services for pregnant women in Bulgaria was performed. The results of the analysis show the opinion of included observation through participation in Wellness activities for pregnant women in different trimesters. Percentage data for preferred place and form of Wellness services. Positive impact of Recreational activities during pregnancy was assessed. SWOT analysis of the development of wellness programs for pregnant women, both threats and opportunities for development. The situational analysis showed that research in the field of wellness and in a specific contingent, pregnant women, is essential regarding healthy lifestyle and social integration. The results highlight the need for further research and implementation of innovative movement practices to improve health status and quality of life in pregnant women.

Keywords: health, motor activity, pregnancy, recreational services, wellness lifestyle

Introduction

In the modern Bulgarian living conditions, conditions for healthy Recreational services for women with normal pregnancies are needed [1]. According to researchers [2] there is a need to establish more and more specialised centers and to offer new, affordable, and different types of Wellness services to meet the needs of pregnant women who want to engage in motor programs. As well, as campaigns and initiatives aimed at better and mass awareness of these women. According to [3], interest in physical activities has been growing in recent years due to their significant impact on the health of the population. Wellness quality of life depends on the economic development of wellness and spa services in Bulgaria, on educational policy and innovation in recreational practices for pregnant women [4, 5]. Recreational wellness programs, and in particular those specific to pregnant women, can be effective prevention with high social impact [6] as participants in wellness programs increase their performance and energy potential [7]. Author [8] points out that motor activity for all is "a vital element of health, fitness, vitality and longevity of man, a factor for improving people's lives". Along with the beneficial impact that engaging in recreational motor activities has on a person's health and body, physical activity in general has a strong social nature and functions. One of the conclusions of the Council of the EU and the Representatives of the Governments of the Member States [9] mentions that: "Lack of physical activity has negative consequences not only for the health of the individual but also for health systems and the economy as a whole, due to the

significant direct and indirect economic costs associated with physical inactivity. The Bulgarian educational model for specialised staff (specialists) plays a key role in the quality of physical activity services for pregnant women [10]. Some authors have investigated the effectiveness of wellness practices in normal pregnancies with innovative programs [11], while others have proposed aqua spinning programs as anti-stress prevention for the health of expectant mothers [12]. All of these may be effective prevention with high social impact. Practicing wellness programs in pregnant women improves their psycho-emotional status, which is in direct interdependence and reflects on the harmonious growth of the fetus [11]. Results of authors studies show that pregnant women with physical activity reduce the incidence of preterm birth, improve not only their quality of life, but are subjected to less stress [13, 14]. Recreational motor activities and wellness practices have been found to be the healthiest social activities that contribute to sustainable development [15]. Wellness and recreation are nowadays a unique means of achieving physical and mental balance, according to some advanced authors [16]. The increased demand for recreational activities links wellness practices and the economy into an inextricable whole [17], including workplace sport in Bulgaria [20].

Methods

The aim of the present study is to identify some marketing aspects related to the provision of Recreational services for pregnant women with normal pregnancies and postpartum women as a prerequisite for improving their quality. *Research objectives:* Task 1.

Study of the literature related to the effects of recreational activities for pregnant woman. Task 2. Carry out a situational analysis of the development of Wellness services for pregnant women in Bulgaria. The subject of this study is the state of the market for recreational motor services for pregnant women. A total of pregnant women 100 with normal pregnancies and 40 postpartum women were the subjects of the study. *The following methods were used:* systematic review, survey with alternative and open-ended responses to questions posed in a questionnaire, SWOT analysis by obtaining information on marketing aspects in the management of Wellness services for pregnant women. Situational analysis - used to formulate trends and conclusions for the development and management of Recreational services for pregnant women in Bulgaria, based on an analysis of their strengths (S - strengths) and weaknesses (W - weaknesses), as well as the resulting opportunities (O - opportunities) and threats (T - threats) to them [18, 19].

Results

Case study through participant observation (participant observation). Participant observation is expressed by the involvement of the researcher for a certain period of time in various activities in the system under study. In order to implement the research and clarify some social and marketing aspects, the activities of organizations offering Wellness services for pregnant women were observed. Figure 1 shows that the largest percentage (62%) of female respondents were between the ages of 26 and 35, with the remainder distributed as follows: 25% from 19 to 25, 13% from 36 to 45, and with 0% each remaining in the age ranges up to 18 and over 45. The results show that in the first trimester of pregnancy 60% of women would prefer intensive (active) Recreational activities and services, while 40% prefer passive (relaxing) ones.

Figure 1. Distribution by age

The choice of Wellness services in the first trimester of pregnancy is largely influenced by the woman's lifestyle before pregnancy. If she has led an active

and dynamic life, it is logical that she would also prefer this type of Recreational services and vice versa.

Table 1.

Recreational motor services preferred by the pregnant women		
Pregnancy period	Intensive (active)	Passive (relaxing)
First trimester	60%	40%
Second trimester	50%	50%
Third trimester	15%	85%

The results for the second trimester are equal, 50% each for active and passive. For the third trimester, the results are perfectly logical. Considering the progression of pregnancy and the physical changes that accompany it, it is quite normal that 85% of the women surveyed would prefer passive (relaxing) services. Preferring active activities were 15%. Figures 2 and 3 reflect

how and where respondent women would prefer to use Wellness motor activities for pregnant women. The results are closely related to the Wellness services practiced by the respondents and those they would like to practice.

Figure 2. Preferred location for using Wellness **Figure 3.** Preferred form of using Wellness services for pregnant women services for pregnant women

A large majority (62%) of women prefer to practice their chosen Wellness in a sports/fitness club or centre, 48% prefer to do so under the supervision of a qualified instructor or coach, and 45% prefer organised, group activities. Confirmation of these results are the selected sports services in the top positions: gymnastics, water aerobics, yoga, swimming, dancing. Of the respondents, 30% would like to participate in outdoor Recreational activities in nature. Women preferring to

train at home and alone are 8% and 7% respectively. This is probably due to lack of financial resources, suitable or difficult transport, also lack of social contact that most young people seek, etc. Figure 4 shows that 90% of the pregnant women surveyed felt that playing Wellness programs had a positive impact on them during their pregnancy. Of these, 7% indicated 'rather yes' and only 3% of women could not judge the impact of playing Recreational activities on them.

Assessing the positive impact

Figure 4. Assessment of the positive impact of Wellness programs during pregnancy

Because of the SWOT analysis, we identified specific findings and influencing factors, described below in Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 2.

SWOT - analysis of the development of Wellness services for pregnant women

WEAK SIDE	STRENGTHS
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Most of the clubs offering sports services for pregnant women lack specialized staffing, i.e. there are no trained coaches/instructors to work with these women. Most of the Wellness services offered to pregnant women are uniform - lacking variety and creativity. Clubs do not have dedicated marketing and advertising departments to exploit the opportunities of the marketing environment. A large number of clubs offer Wellness services for pregnant women as a complement to their main activity. They do not have specially developed programmes to work with them. Many clubs do not require a recommendation from an obstetrician-gynaecologist about the health status of the pregnant woman. There is a lack of linkage and communication between clubs offering Wellness services for pregnant women and medical and hospital facilities. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> More and more women appreciate the positive impact of playing Wellness during their pregnancy. The majority of the clubs have established a relatively effective economic mechanism for self-financing of the Wellness services offered and for stimulating the work of sports professionals. Many of the sports clubs and centres offering Wellness services for pregnant women have well established facilities of their own. Some of the sports centres have a relatively well-established promotional policy to stimulate their customers. An innovative holistic program (scientific product) for women with normal pregnancies was created at the National Sports Academy "V. Levski", Sofia. A set of documents is required – a recommendation from an obstetrician-gynaecologist, a declaration of informed consent Many of the women using Wellness services for pregnant women have a clear and specific motivation for doing so.

Table 3.

SWOT – analysis for threats and development opportunities

CAPS	DEVELOPMENT OPPORTUNITIES
<p>1. The underestimation of the need for Wellness activities for pregnant women by government officials and politicians as a means to protect and improve the health status and vitality of the population.</p> <p>2. The unprofessional, inconsistent and under-researched provision of Wellness services for pregnant women.</p> <p>3. Poor advertising of this type of Wellness services and the low level of awareness of potential users.</p> <p>4. The decreasing population trend in Bulgaria and in particular the number of women.</p>	<p>1. Optimization of the organizational and management structures of the clubs. Establish marketing departments, carrying out the overall marketing policy of the clubs.</p> <p>2. Improving the quality of the Wellness services offered, including hiring qualified sports specialists to work with pregnant women, developing tailored training programmes.</p> <p>3. The lack of variety in the Wellness services for pregnant women offered on the market, as well as the small number of sports clubs/centres offering such services is a favourable prerequisite for the development and market introduction of new and creative services.</p> <p>4. Expanding the activities of the clubs/centres offering sports services for pregnant women, by focusing their efforts on offering sports-educational knowledge to expectant mothers in various forms- courses, seminars, etc.</p> <p>5. Creating initiatives and campaigns aimed at better awareness of pregnant women and attracting them as potential users of Wellness services.</p> <p>6. Creation and implementation of a national strategy for the development of physical activity and Wellness for pregnant women.</p> <p>7. Creation and implementation of modern national and regional programs for the development and promotion of Wellness among pregnant women.</p>

Discussion

This SWOT – analysis was prepared based on a market research on the interest of pregnant women for active Wellness activities and an analysis of the situation of sports clubs and centres offering services for pregnant women. In carrying out this analysis, the current state of the market for Recreational services for pregnant women in the current socio-economic conditions was taken into account. Bulgaria is with many innovations in various fields and it can be boldly stated that the wellness practices in 2010 include the Nesheva holistic program for women with normal pregnancy. It is necessary to work for the promotion of such scientific models that have social relevance. Creation and implementation of regional programmes for the development and promotion of Recreation during pregnancy is a task with multiple social benefits.

Conclusion

The analysis shows that the main reserves for the development and improvement of Recreational services for pregnant women are expressed in the following areas:

- ✓ Human resources (including Wellness /sports specialists and advertising specialists);
- ✓ Expanding and diversifying the clubs' activities and services and medical provision;
- ✓ Communication and links with other institutions and organisations;
- ✓ Optimisation of the organisational and management structures of the clubs (including the establishment of marketing departments) and the development of an active marketing policy in line with market conditions;
- ✓ Consumer research and consideration.

Note:

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An agreement for informed consent to publishing data was signed.

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